

HEART TRANSPLANTATION IN ENGLISH CARDIAC SURGERY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to revealing the importance of heart transplantation using the example of the English experience. The following are various recommendations and warnings for heart transplantation.

ТРАНСПЛАНТАЦИЯ СЕРДЦА В АНГЛИЙСКОЙ КАРДИОХИРУРГИИ

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ABSTRACT

Данная статья посвящена раскрытию значение трансплантации сердца на примере опыта Англии. Ниже приводятся различные рекомендации и предупреждения при трансплантации сердца.

Cardiology is a branch of medicine that studies the structure, functions and diseases of the heart and blood vessels, as well as develops methods for their diagnosis, treatment and prevention.

In addition, the problems of medical rehabilitation of people with lesions of the cardiovascular system lie in the field of cardiology.

Cardiac surgery is the treatment of congenital or acquired heart diseases through surgical intervention.

Today, British cardiologists have at their disposal a variety of methods for accurate and reliable examination of the condition of the heart and effective treatment options.

A heart transplant is a surgical operation to replace the heart of a patient (recipient) with the heart of a donor.

Heart transplantation is indicated for severe heart diseases in which other operations are impossible or extremely risky, and life expectancy without a heart transplant is low.

Indications for it are end-stage heart failure, cardiomyopathy of various origins, inoperable congenital heart defects, benign heart tumors, severe ischemic disease and other pathology.

A heart transplant requires compatibility of the tissues of the patient (recipient) and the donor, and this does not happen often.

Currently, more than 3,000 heart transplants are performed in more than 330 clinics around the world every year.

English specialists are constantly working on studying and developing new methods of heart treatment and improving their skills.

In 1980, Professor Sir Magdi Jakub performed the UK's first heart transplant at the Harfield Clinic.

Royal Brompton and Harefield is the UK's largest center for the diagnosis and treatment of heart diseases (including congenital heart defects) and lungs.

Treatment of cardiac pathology is carried out in many clinics in England at the highest level.

For example, at the Harley Street Clinic, specialists perform heart surgery in children, including organ transplantation.

In the clinic, you can undergo a qualitative study of cardiovascular pathologies and their treatment.

Diagnosis and treatment of cardiac diseases in England can be carried out in Cardiology centers and multidisciplinary clinics.

Cardiology clinics and departments in England provide their patients with a full range of services for the diagnosis and treatment of heart diseases.

British clinics use only modern technology. The clinics are equipped with the most modern medical equipment.

Treatment in clinics in England guarantees accurate diagnosis, the best hospital conditions, and comfortable postoperative care.

UK guidelines for referral and assessment of adults for heart transplantation:

Patients with advanced heart failure have a dismal prognosis and poor quality of life. Heart transplantation provides an effective treatment for a subset of these patients. This article provides cardiologists with up-to-date information about referral for transplantation, the role of left ventricular assist devices prior to transplant, patient selection, waiting-list management and donor heart availability. Timing is of central importance; patients should be referred before complications (eg, cardiorenal syndrome or secondary pulmonary hypertension) have developed that will increase the risk of, or potentially contraindicate, transplantation. Issues related to heart failure aetiology, comorbidity and adherence to

medical treatment are reviewed. Finally, the positive role that cardiologists can play in promoting and facilitating organ donation is discussed.

Assessment of the potential heart donor: a role for biomarkers:

Demand for donor hearts exceeds supply, and a significant number of patients die while awaiting transplantation. Within the pool of currently unused potential donor hearts, a proportion may be suitable for transplantation but are declined due to anticipated poor function. Despite current assessment methods, in some donor hearts accepted for transplantation early graft failure develops in the recipient. Current methods of assessment are inadequate, and there is a potential for biomarkers to improve identification of satisfactory hearts for transplantation or hearts destined to fail in the recipient. Biomarkers are routinely used to diagnose and risk-stratify myocardial infarction, acute coronary syndromes, and heart failure. Some of these might facilitate donor heart assessment. Cardiac troponins, cytokines, inflammatory markers, natriuretic peptides, and intracellular proteins may each have discriminant value. This review details the current status of biomarkers in the assessment of donor hearts.

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